

THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND PERCEPTION OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE ON JOB SATISFACTION: A CASE STUDY ON FLIGHT ATTENDANT

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1. Introduction

Organizational justice is the most crucial component in increasing employee job satisfaction. As a result, the impression of justice is the aspect that allows people to function securely in the organizational working environment. The foundation of organizational management is organizational justice. According to studies, in contexts where employees' views of organizational justice are strong, their job satisfaction rises and their feeling of commitment to corporate goals rises (Özkan, 2018: 53).

According to research, as workers' knowledge of justice improves, so does their job satisfaction; conversely, as workers' understanding of justice deteriorates, so does their job satisfaction. Furthermore, research on how to boost job happiness suggests that the impression of justice has a considerable impact on job satisfaction (Yelboğa, 2012: 173).

It is critical in today's enterprises to guarantee organizational commitment and employee job satisfaction. As a result, work satisfaction and organizational commitment are frequently studied in the literature. Employees can be protected by organizations satisfying their personal and institutional requirements. Employees require institutions in which they may find tranquility and enjoy their job. It is extremely beneficial to do the appropriate research and measures in order to sustain these attitudes and ensure that workers are content with their jobs and remain loyal to their businesses.

High job satisfaction strengthens organizational commitment. Additionally, great organizational commitment might lead to work satisfaction. However, the lack of research on the influence of organizational commitment on work satisfaction raises the value of this study, which is expected to contribute to the literature and practice.

The purpose of this study is to see if flight attendants' loyalty to their employers and their opinions of organizational justice impact their work happiness.

2. Organizational commitment

Individual conduct is a representation of his commitment, and hence commitment may be understood based on what the individual shows to the other party (Salancik, 1977: 27). Loyalty to a business can be member-based since the events that result in the member's loyalty are centered on their prior conduct (Angel and Perry, 1983: 31). Organizational commitment is described as a circumstance in which an employee identifies with the organization's goals and wishes to continue working for the organization in order to help it achieve those goals (Blau and Boal, 1987: 290). It is a stage in which the organization's and the employee's goals become more integrated or complementary (Hall et al., 1970: 176).

The level of dedication reflects the outcomes of organizational dedication. In this context, organizational commitment is investigated at three levels: (i) low, (ii) normal (moderate), and (iii) high, as well as its positive and negative repercussions (Randall, 1987: 463). In the low-level organizational commitment type, the employee's commitment to his organization is weak. However, they must remain in the organization for a variety of reasons (Bayram, 2005: 125). Employees are expected to quit the company if the relevant circumstances are satisfied (Balay, 2000:

12). This degree of dedication is referred to as "responsibility commitment" or "continuance loyalty" (Randall, 1987: 465). Employees respect the presence of the organization in the usual (moderate) organizational commitment type, and as their stay in the organization rises, their desire to quit the company reduces. This level of dedication is known as "formal commitment" or "normative commitment" (Randall, 1987: 467). Employees' commitment to the organization is especially strong in cases of high organizational commitment. Employees with this level of commitment stay with the business for a long time and do not wish to quit lightly (Bayram, 2005: 127). This level of dedication is known as "identification" or "emotional commitment" (Randall, 1987: 468).

3. Job satisfaction

The dictionary defines pleasure as "making the desired come true, pleasing the heart, satisfaction" (TDK, 2020). It is used in everyday language to convey an individual's inner tranquility (Yılmaz, 2015: 37). This joy or peace of mind leads to job satisfaction when individuals working in the organization meet their goals (Görgülüer, 2013: 74).

Hackman and Odham defined job satisfaction as employees' contentment at their workplace. Individuals' emotional reactions to their employment are crucial in terms of employee loyalty, continuity, and productivity (Schmidt, 2009: 297). Job satisfaction, according to Locke, is the satisfaction or pleasant emotional thinking that arises as a result of an individual's judgment of his or her job or job experiences. Job satisfaction, according to Mosadeghrad, is "the emotional response of employees to their occupations based on the determined and resultant results." Employee happiness with their work enables the successful utilization of human capital, which has become more vital for enterprises (Vila and Garcia-Mora, 2005: 127). A person who develops favorable habits toward his or her employment retains these positive behaviors outside of the workplace. If an employee is dissatisfied with his job, he cannot be pleased in activities unrelated to his employment. Inability to cultivate a positive attitude toward one's employment can also lead to job discontent (Gavcar & Topaloğlu, 2008: 4).

A high degree of job satisfaction reflects a high level of individual fulfillment. The work itself, the compensation, the management style, and the employee's colleagues are all elements that influence the employee's job satisfaction level (Tutar, 2007: 19). Organizations benefit from high levels of success as a result of high levels of employee satisfaction.

Job satisfaction is crucial for both individuals and businesses for two reasons:

- **The Importance of Job Satisfaction for Employees:** Organizations and bosses frequently do not mind if their employees are worried, uncomfortable, or hesitant, arguing that employees should become accustomed to this scenario. However, it should not be forgotten that the importance of work done to improve employee job happiness is defined by the employers. Employers should seek to boost their workers' job happiness while also increasing their productivity. When companies work for their employees' happiness, both their job satisfaction and commitment to work grow. In this situation, the corporation must maintain peace and enhance output (Lyman et al., 2003; Özkan, 2018: 67).

- **The Importance of Job Satisfaction for Businesses:** When employees' work satisfaction levels are high or poor, it reflects both their social environment on the job and their social environment in their personal life. Individuals who are unhappy at work frequently experience mood fluctuations such as quitting, squandering time, melancholy, worry, and anxiety. Individuals who are dissatisfied with their jobs are less committed to them. One of the most challenging and vital jobs of senior managers is to ensure employee work satisfaction. Managers seek to assure their workers' job satisfaction levels for the three reasons listed below. He stated that high employee job satisfaction levels increase productivity and the reason for employee absenteeism or commitment to the job is determined by their job satisfaction level, and that managers should take responsibility for motivating their employees and increasing their job satisfaction levels.

Job satisfaction is undeniably important in terms of influencing employees' physical and emotional health, organizational efficiency, and job performance. In terms of the outcomes it produces, job happiness is individual and organizational, as well as societal. Its existence is a highly desired phenomenon in this respect, although it is not always available. Job satisfaction is greatly desired by managers when it comes to generating excellent working circumstances. Unwanted behaviors such as slowing down work, inefficiency, indiscipline, and absenteeism can be observed in firms when employees are dissatisfied with their jobs (Davis, 1988: 95).

4. Organizational justice

Organizational justice is a notion concerned with workplace behavior decisions and how these actions impact work-related aspects (Moorman, 1991: 845). It is characterized as a reflection of equitable and fair behaviors (Çağ, 2001: 12).

Folger and Cropanzano describe organizational justice as the procedures used to make judgments about the allocation of organizational resources, as well as the social norms and regulations that govern people's interactions when these methods are applied. This perspective emerges when workers establish certain criteria and assess whether they are treated with respect based on these factors (Altinkurt and Yılmaz, 2010: 275).

5. Method

5.1. Purpose of the Research

The objective of this study is to see how organizational commitment and organizational justice affect work satisfaction among flight attendants. The study also looked into whether the cabin crew's judgments of organizational commitment, work happiness, and organizational justice changed based on their demographics.

5.2. Research Method

The study is a descriptive study that employs the survey model, which is one of the quantitative research methodologies. The survey model may be used without interfering with the researcher's current condition to determine the features of occurrences or instances that impact each other (Karasar, 2009: 77).

The model of the research is presented in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Research Model

The hypotheses to be tested in the research are as follows. *Hypothesis 1: Employees' organizational commitment affects their job satisfaction. Hypothesis 1a: Employees' emotional commitment affects their job satisfaction. Hypothesis 1b: Employees' normative commitment affects their job satisfaction. Hypothesis 1c: Employees' continuance commitment affects their job satisfaction. Hypothesis 2: Employees' organizational justice affects their job satisfaction. Hypothesis 2a: Employees' interactional and procedural justice affects their job satisfaction. Hypothesis 2b: Distributive justice of employees affects their job satisfaction.*

5.3. Population and Sampling of the Research

The population of the research has been established to be roughly 17.000 cabin attendants, albeit this fluctuates on a regular basis in civilian aircraft businesses operating in January 2020, with Istanbul Airport as the hub (GDCA, 2019). The confidence level was accepted as 95 percent for determining the sample size, and the allowable error amount was +/-5 percent (Yazıcıoğlu and Erdoğan, 2004: 3). As a result, the lowest limit of the study's valid sample size was judged to be 377. The cabin crew was chosen as the study's sample using an easily available sampling procedure. Due to time and budgetary restrictions, the readily available sampling approach allows working with an easily accessible sample group (Baltacı, 2018: 22).

5.4. Data Collection Tools

The research utilized the "Personal Information Form," "Organizational Commitment Scale," "Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale," and "Organizational Justice Scale." It is a query in the personal information form that attempts to learn the gender, age, marital status, education, position in the cabin, and year employed. The organizational commitment scale is divided into three sub-dimensions. Affective commitment, continuous commitment, and normative commitment are the three aspects. The Organizational Commitment Scale's Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was determined as 0.683 (Doan, 2013: 18).

The organizational commitment scale is the first scale utilized as a data gathering instrument. The dimensions of this scale were discovered to be three factors as a result of the factor analysis. This includes emotional commitment (6 items), normative commitment (4 items), and persistence commitment (2 items). The affective commitment dimension factor loads vary from 0.885 to 0.726, the normative commitment dimension component loads from 0.861 to 0.758, and the continuity commitment dimension factor loads from 0.800 to 0.785. Items having factor loads less than 0.50 and gathered under several factors were not evaluated. A total of 12 items were subjected to factor analysis.

Table 1 indicates the results of the validity and reliability analysis of the organizational commitment scale.

Table 1. Organizational Commitment Scale Validity and Reliability Results

	Factor Loads
Emotional Commitment (Variance Ratio= 35,507, Cronbach Alpha=0,913, n=6)	
6. The institution I work for means a lot to me.	0,885
4. I feel "emotionally connected" to the organization I work for.	0,852
5. I see myself as "part of the family" in the institution I work for.	0,849
3. I feel that I belong to the institution I work for.	0,844
2. I really feel that the issues of the institution I work for are my own.	0,738
1. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my professional life in the institution where I work.	0,726
Normative Commitment (Variance Ratio=23,056, Cronbach Alpha=0,828, n=4)	
10. I do not think of leaving my institution because I do not have many alternatives.	0,861
9. My life would be turned upside down if I were to leave my current institution.	0,807
8. Even if I wanted to, I am not in a position to leave my current institution.	0,794
12. If I leave the institution I work for, my opportunity to find another job will be limited.	0,758
Continuance Commitment (Variance Ratio= 12,921, Cronbach Alpha= 0,600, n=2)	
13. I do not feel an obligation to continue working in this institution.	0,800
17. I can't leave my organization right now because I feel obligated to the people here.	0,785
Organizational Commitment Scale (Total Variance Ratio=71,484, General Cronbach Alpha=0,714, n= 12, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test Value=0,817, Bartlett Sphericity Test Value (X ²)=2861,36, p=0,000)	

Exploratory Factor Analysis was realized to measure the validity of the organizational commitment scale. KMO was used to measure the factor analysis of the scale, the Bartlett Sphericity test was used to measure the consistency between the items, Principal Component Analysis was used to determine the factors, and the Varimax method was chosen as the rotation process to maximize the variance. In order to determine the reliability of the scale, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was tried to be specified.

The KMO test value of the organizational commitment scale is 0.817 (KMO=0.90<81.7≤0.80). This ratio shows that the scale is well suited for factor analysis. The subsequent Bartlett Test of Sphericity was found to be significant

($X^2=2861.36$, $p=0.000 \leq 0.01$). Thus, it was determined that there was no relationship between the items of the scale. In other words, the consistency of the 12 items of the scale was ensured.

After all this process, it was determined that the scale consisted of three factors. The first factor consists of six items and is called affective commitment. The variance percentage of the affective commitment factor was 35.5% and the Cronbach alpha coefficient was determined as 0.913. In this frame, the items belonging to this factor are highly reliable. The second factor consists of four items and is called normative commitment. The percentage of the variance of this factor was 23.1% and the Cronbach alpha coefficient was determined as 0.828. In this context, the items belonging to this factor are reliable at a good level. The third factor consists of two items and is called continuance commitment. The variance percentage of the continuance commitment factor was 12.9% and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was determined as 0.600, and the items of this factor were moderately reliable. The total variance percentage of the organizational commitment scale is 71.5% and the Cronbach alpha coefficient obtained for the overall reliability of the scale is 0.714, which points out that the scale is reliable at a good level.

The job satisfaction scale is the second data-gathering technique employed. The dimensions were determined to be the only factor in the factor analysis for this scale. The scale's factor loadings ranged from 0.891 to 0.728. Items with a factor load of less than 0.50 and gathered under several factors were not analyzed. A total of eight items were subjected to factor analysis. Table 2 indicates the results of the validity and reliability analysis of the job satisfaction scale.

Table 2. Validity and Reliability Results of the Job Satisfaction Scale

	Factor Loads
19. In terms of being appreciated for a good job I have done	0,891
17. In terms of working conditions	0,885
18. In terms of my colleagues' agreement with each other	0,858
6. In terms of my supervisor's decision-making competence	0,851
14. In order to have the opportunity to be promoted in the job	0,851
5. In terms of my supervisor's management style	0,844
12. In terms of the implementation of business decisions	0,832
9. In terms of having the opportunity to do things for others	0,728
Job Satisfaction Scale (Total Variance Ratio=71,183, General Cronbach Alpha=0,942,n=8 KMO Test Value=0,905, X2 Value=2787,59, p=0,000)	

The job satisfaction scale's KMO test value is 0.905 (KMO=1.0090.59.90). This ratio demonstrates that the scale is ideal for factor analysis. The subsequent Bartlett Test of Sphericity revealed a significant result ($X^2=2787.59$, $p=0.000\leq 0.01$). As a consequence, it was determined that there was no relationship between the scale's items. In other words, the consistency of the scale's eight items was ensured. The job satisfaction scale's percentage of the total variance is 71.2 percent, and the Cronbach alpha coefficient obtained for the scale's reliability is 0.942, indicating that the scale has a high level of reliability.

Interactional and procedural justice dimensions (14 items) combined to form a factor after factor analysis for this article. As the second factor, the distributive justice dimension (5 items) was also determined. The interactional and procedural justice dimensions had factor loads ranging from 0.873 to 0.642, while the distributive justice dimension had factor loads ranging from 0.874 to 0.726. Items with a factor load of less than 0.50 and collected under various factors were not analyzed. A total of nineteen items were applied to factor analysis.

Table 3 shows the results of the validity and reliability analysis of the organizational justice scale.

Table 3. Validity and Reliability Results of the Organizational Justice Scale

	Factor Loads
Interactional and Procedural Justice (Variance Ratio=50,925, Cronbach Alpha=0,979, n=14)	
17. My managers discuss the consequences of my business decisions with me.	0,873
18. My managers give appropriate reasons for decisions about my business.	0,853
15. While making decisions about my job, my managers are honest and sincere with me.	0,852
19. While making decisions about my job, my managers give me reasonable explanations.	0,852
13. While making decisions about my job, my managers treat me with respect and give importance to me.	0,840
14. While making business decisions, my managers are sensitive to my personal needs.	0,823
16. When making decisions about my job, my managers observe my rights as an employee.	0,819
11. Employees may oppose the managers' decisions regarding work or may request that these decisions be re-negotiated by the higher authorities.	0,806
8. Managers collect accurate and complete information before making business decisions.	0,785

12. When making decisions about my job, my managers treat me with kindness and concern.	0,785
7. Managers take the opinions of all employees before making business decisions.	0,753
9. Managers explain the decisions taken to the employees and provide additional information when requested.	0,715
10. All work-related decisions apply to all employees affected by them without discrimination.	0,704
6. Business decisions are handled impartially by managers.	0,642
Distributive Justice (Variance Ratio=28,771, Cronbach Alpha=0,936, n=5)	
4. Taken as a whole, I think the gains I have made from my workplace are fair.	0,874
2. I believe my salary is fair.	0,834
3. I think my workload is fair.	0,792
5. I believe that my job responsibilities are fair.	0,767
1. My work schedule is fair.	0,726
Organizational Justice Scale (Total Variance Ratio=79,696, General Cronbach Alpha=0,979, n=19 KMO Test Value=0,954, X2 Value= 10572,46, p=0,000)	

The KMO test value of the organizational justice scale is 0.954 ($KMO=1.00 < 95.4 \leq 0.90$). This ratio shows that the scale is perfectly suitable for factor analysis. The subsequent Bartlett Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($X^2=10572.46, p=0.000 \leq 0.01$). Thus, it was determined that there was no relationship between the items on the scale. In other words, the consistency of the nineteen items of the scale was ensured.

After all of this, it was determined that the scale was made up of two factors. The first factor, interactional and procedural justice, consists of fourteen items. This factor's variance percentage was 50.9 %, and Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.979. This factor's items are extremely reliable in this framework. The second factor, known as distributive justice, consists of five items. This factor's percentage of variance was 28.8 %, and the Cronbach alpha coefficient was 0.936. This factor's items are extremely reliable in this context.

The total variance percentage of the organizational justice scale is 79.7% and the Cronbach alpha coefficient acquired for the overall reliability of the scale is 0.979, which shows that the scale is highly reliable.

5.5. Limitations

The research is limited to 322 cabin crew and 85 cabin attendants departing from the duty-free zone at Istanbul Airport. The research was conducted between 02 February 2020 and 30 March 2020. This process coincided with the pandemic (global epidemic), which was experienced throughout the world and whose effect was felt intensely in Turkey. Flight attendants, the study's target group, may have assumed that because they were in pandemic conditions, officers with organizational justice would have no effect on their job satisfaction.

6. Findings

6.1. Personal Information Questions

Personal information questions were asked to determine the gender, age, marital status, education level, duty position, and working years in the cabin of the cabin crew and their supervisors, and the distribution of the collected information was assessed.

Ultimately, the distribution of personal characteristics of 407 cabin crew and their supervisors was examined. 55.8% (n=227) of the employees are women and 44.2% (n=180) are men. 69.8% (n=284) of these individuals were in the 22-28 age group, 18.4% (n=75) were in the 29-35 age group, and 11.8% (n=48) were in the 36 and above age group. Looking at their marital status, 75.2% (n=306) of the civil servants are single and 24.8% (n=101) are married. 47.4% (n=193) of the participants were high school and associate degree graduates, 41.0% (n=167) undergraduate and 11.5% (n=47) postgraduate degrees. While 79.1% (n=322) of the working population participating in the research are cabin attendants, 20.9% (n=85) are cabin supervisors. Lastly, the personal characteristics examined are the working years of the cabin crew. 69.0% (n=281) of the cabin workers are between 1-5 years, 18.4% (n=75) are between 6-10 years, 12.5% (n=51) are 11 years and above works.

6.2. Difference Tests

This section discusses whether or not organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and organizational justice scores differ based on demographic characteristics. On the basis of the meaningful results, interpretations are made.

The normative commitment of the general organizational commitment of the married cabin crew differs from the general organizational commitment and normative commitment of the single employees. Married civil servants have a high level of organizational commitment, but they also feel obligated to stay in the

organization out of a sense of duty and responsibility. The cabin crew's general organizational justice perceptions, interactional and procedural justice perceptions, distributive justice perceptions, and general job satisfaction differ from those of the cabin supervisors. Flight attendants have higher general job satisfaction with general justice perceptions, interactional and procedural perceptions, and distributive justice perceptions.

There was a difference in general organizational commitment and normative commitment between cabin employees over the age of 36 and those between the ages of 22 and 28. Employees aged 36 and over are more committed to the company and their jobs, and they consider themselves obligated to work. There was a difference in continuance commitment, general organizational justice perceptions, interactional and procedural justice perceptions, and distributive justice between employees aged 22 to 28 when compared to those aged 36 and older. Cabin workers in the 22-28 age group think that they need to stay in their organization, claiming that they have a more just attitude. They believe that in the workplace, every employee is given equal opportunities and that they have a positive impact on their coworkers. There was a difference between employees in the 29-35 age group compared to the 22-28 age group in terms of normative and continuing commitments. Cabin employees aged 29 to 35 believe that staying in the organization is required for their responsibilities, whereas those aged 22 to 28 believe that staying in the organization is simply a necessity.

Employees with a high school diploma and an associate degree have different perceptions of general, interactional, procedural, and distributive justice than those with a bachelor's degree. Cabin attendants with a high school diploma or an associate's degree believe they seem fairer. At the same time, they claimed that in their workplace, every employee is given equal opportunities and that they have a positive impact on their colleagues.

When the differences in organizational commitment, perceptions of organizational justice and job satisfaction of flight attendants according to their working hours are assessed, the general organizational commitment and normative commitment of employees of 11 years and over compared to those of 1-5 years; There was a difference between the normative commitments of those who worked between 6-10 years compared to those who worked between 1-5 years, and between general, interactional and procedural and distributive justice perceptions in those who worked between 1-5 years compared to those who worked for 11 years or more. The experiences gained by the employees for 11 years or more during their stay in the organization cause an increase in their general organizational commitment and cause them to feel that it is necessary to stay in the organization due to their sense of duty and the responsibilities they take. They feel that it is an obligation to stay in the organization depending on the responsibilities they take with the awareness. It is

thought that in the group working between 1-5 years, they treat all employees in the organization more customarily, that all opportunities are distributed equally and with the right method, and that they also affect all other employees properly.

6.3. Simple and Linear Regression Analysis

The impact of organizational commitment and dimensions, organizational justice, and cabin crew dimensions on job satisfaction was tried to be examined using simple and multiple linear regression analysis.

Table 4 shows the results of the simple regression analysis regarding the job satisfaction effect of the organizational commitment of the employees.

Table 4. Simple Regression Analysis Results on the Effect of Employee Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction.

		<i>B</i>	<i>S.E.</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	Adjusted <i>R</i> ²	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
General Job Satisfaction	(Invariant)	,632	,253		2,498	,013					
	General Organizational Commitment	,829	,068	,517	12,145	,000	,517	,267	0,265	147,511	,000

According to the results of simple regression analysis, it is seen that general organizational commitment explains 26.5% (Adjusted R²=0.265) of overall job satisfaction. The model is significant according to the ANOVA test results showing the effect of the fixed variable and independent variable (general organizational commitment) on the dependent variable (general job satisfaction) (F=147.511, p=0.000≤0.01). It has been specified that the general organizational commitment of the employees ($\beta = 0.517$) affects their job satisfaction. Therefore, hypothesis 1 was partially accepted. The simple linear regression model is given below.

$$\text{General Job Satisfaction} = 0,632 + 0,829 * \text{General Organizational Commitment}$$

Table 5 shows the results of multiple regression analysis regarding the effect of organizational commitment dimensions on job satisfaction.

Table 5. Multiple Regression Analysis Results on the Effects of Organizational Commitment Dimensions on Job Satisfaction

		<i>B</i>	<i>S.E.</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	Adjusted <i>R</i> ²	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
General Job Satisfaction	(Invariant)	,678	0,92	0,1	,534	3,000					
	Emotional Commitment	,616	0,39	0,0	,561	5,651					
	Normative Commitment	0,097	-0,28	0,0	-0,116	-3,535	,763	,583	,580	187,718	,000
	Continuance Commitment	,256	0,32	0,0	,289	1,104					

Depending on the results of multiple regression analysis, it is seen that affective, normative, and continuance commitments together explain 58.0% (Adjusted R²=0.580) of overall job satisfaction. The model is significant according to the results of the ANOVA test, which shows the effect of the fixed variable and independent variables (emotional, normative, and continuance commitments) on the dependent variable (general job satisfaction) ($F=187,718$, $p=0,000 \leq 0.01$). Affective commitment ($\beta=0.561$), normative commitment ($\beta=-0.116$) and continuance commitment ($\beta=0.289$) were found to affect overall job satisfaction. As a consequence, hypothesis 1a, hypothesis 1b, and hypothesis 1c were accepted. The multiple linear regression model is shown below.

$$\text{General Job Satisfaction} = 0,678 + 0,616 * \text{Emotional Commitment} - 0,097 * \text{Normative Commitment} + 0,256 * \text{Continuance Commitment}$$

Table 6 indicates the results of a simple regression analysis regarding the effect of organizational justice perceptions of employees on job satisfaction.

Table 6. Simple Regression Analysis Results on the Effect of Employees' Perceptions of Organizational Justice on Job Satisfaction

		<i>B</i>	<i>S.E.</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>f</i>
General Job Satisfaction	(Invariant)	3,593	0,139		25,826	0,000	0,249	0,618
	General Organizational Justice	0,020	0,041	0,025	0,499	0,618		

According to the results of the simple regression analysis, the model was not significant according to the results of the ANOVA test, which showed the effect of the independent variable (general organizational justice) on the dependent variable (general job satisfaction) ($F=0.249$, $p=0.618 \geq 0.05$). The general organizational justice of the employees ($\beta = 0.517$) does not affect their job satisfaction. Therefore, *hypothesis 2* was not accepted.

Table 7 shows the results of multiple regression analysis regarding the effect of organizational justice dimensions on job satisfaction.

Table 7. Multiple Regression Analysis Results on the Effects of Organizational Justice Dimensions on Job Satisfaction

		<i>B</i>	<i>S.E.</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>f</i>
General Job Satisfaction	(Invariant)	3,641	0,151		24,092	0,000	0,457	0,634
	Interactional and Procedural Justice	0,060	0,062	0,077	0,956	0,340		
	Distributive Justice	-0,049	0,066	-0,059	-0,740	0,460		

According to the results of the multiple regression analysis, the model was not significant according to the results of the ANOVA test, which showed the effect of the independent variables (interactional and procedural justice and distributive justice) on the dependent variable (general job satisfaction) ($F=0.457$, $p=0.618 \geq 0.01$). The general organizational justice of the employees ($\beta = 0.517$) does not affect their job satisfaction. Therefore, *hypothesis 2a* and *hypothesis 2b* were not rejected.

Result

The study's objective is to scrutinize the effects of flight attendants' and cabin chiefs' perceptions of organizational commitment and justice on job satisfaction. According to the regression analyses, employees' commitment to their organizations has a linear effect on their job satisfaction. Employees' emotional commitment and continuance commitment to their organizations positively affect their normative

commitments and negatively affect their job satisfaction when viewed across dimensions, but their organizational justice perceptions have no effect on their satisfaction with their organizations. The cabin crew's general organizational justice perceptions, interactional and procedural justice perceptions, distributive justice perceptions, and general job satisfaction differ from those of the cabin supervisors. Flight attendants have higher general perceptions of justice, interactional and procedural perceptions, distributive justice perceptions, and overall job satisfaction than pursers.

Married flight attendants are much more loyal to the institution for which they work based on their marital status. Because married people have more responsibilities, they prefer to remain in the institution for a longer period of time. As a matter of fact, they feel obligated to stay in the organization as opposed to single grave officers who have a higher sense of duty and consciousness. Individuals who believe there is justice in the institution for which they work are more satisfied with their work and enjoy their jobs. Employees who notice that employees at the same level and with the same qualifications are treated equally and without favoritism focus on their duties because they believe they will be rewarded (promotion, salary increase, bonus) as a result of their duties. It is impossible to discuss justice in institutions where nepotism exists. This naturally leads to employee job satisfaction; it will have a direct impact on their enjoyment or dissatisfaction with their work. In this situation, the employee's performance will suffer as well. Because the Civil Aviation industry requires teamwork, organizational justice is critical. A policy of equal behavior should be followed by all team members. The concept of cabin safety and security should not be overlooked. Cabin crew members play an important role in ensuring that passengers arrive at their destination in a healthy and efficient manner. Cabin crew members ensure their survival in addition to their primary duty of catering by providing first aid services; thanks to the first aid training they have received, to passengers in case of an emergency. Cabin crew personnel, who are critical to passengers, must have advanced communication skills, be able to manage stress, and be successful in decision-making, team management, leadership, workload management, and crisis and conflict management. According to our findings, in order to achieve all of these goals, organizational justice must be provided, which leads to increased organizational commitment, which leads to increased job satisfaction and employee performance.

The findings of this study are significant in terms of the effects of perceived organizational justice and organizational commitment on job satisfaction. Furthermore, there are few studies that look at the effects of organizational justice dimensions (interactive, procedural, and distributive justice) on job satisfaction and organizational commitment (emotional, continuance, and normative commitment) (Rai, 2013: 28). Thus, the findings of our study are significant in terms of contributing to the literature.

Enterprises can only thrive and thrive if they gain a sustainable competitive advantage. Employees, as internal customers, play a vital role in sustaining competitive advantage. Employees can only perform at the desired level if they are satisfied with their jobs and committed to the organization.

The results of the studies may vary once the effect of this process wears off. Researchers recommend that a similar study be conducted after the pandemic process, with the results compared and analyzed.

Disclosure statement

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XÜLASƏ

Təşkilati öhdəlik və təşkilati ədalət qavramının iş məmnunluğuna təsiri: Kabin məmurlarına istiqamətlənmiş tədqiqat işi

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Bu tədqiqatın məqsədi təşkilati öhdəlik və təşkilati ədalətin iş məmnunluğuna təsirini müəyyən etməkdir. Tədqiqatda əlaqəli skrining modelindən istifadə edilmişdir. Araşdırmanın əsas mərkəzi İstanbul Hava Limanı olmaqla, 2020-ci ilin yanvar ayında fəaliyyət göstərən mülki hava yolu şirkətlərində vaxtaşırı dəyişən təxminən 17.000 kabin bələdçisindən ibarətdir.

Nümunəvi seçmə üsulu ilə 377 kabin məmuru müəyyən edilmişdir. Tədqiqatda məlumatların toplanması üçün Təşkilati Öhdəlik Ölçüsü, Minnesota İş Məmnuniyyəti Ölçüsü və Təşkilati Ədalət Şkalasından istifadə edilmişdir. Məlumatların təhlili üçün proqnozlaşdırılan dəyişikliklər Çox Xətli Reqressiya Analizindən istifadə edilmişdir. Araşdırma nəticəsində bəlli olmuşdur ki, təyyarə bələdçilərinin təşkilati bağlılığı və qoyulan ölçülər kontekstində baxıldığında işçilərin emosional, davamlılıq və normativ öhdəlikləri birlikdə iş məmnuniyyətinə təsir edir. Kabin heyətinin təşkilati ədaləti onların iş məmnunluğuna da öz təsirini göstərir. Qoyulan tələblər çərçivəsində baxıldıqda, qarşılıqlı, prosessual və paylaşılan ədalətin birlikdə qavranılması iş məmnuniyyətinə təsirini göstərmir.

Açar sözlər: Təşkilati öhdəlik, təşkilati ədalət, işdən məmnunluq, mülki aviasiya, kabin məmuru

JEL Kodlar:M1, M12, M54

РЕЗЮМЕ**Влияние организационного обязательства и восприятия организационной справедливости на удовлетворенность работой: Исследование, направленное на кабинетных чиновников****Эрдал ДУРСУН***Университет Нишанташи, Турция***Месут ОЗТИРАК***Стамбульский университет Эсенюрт, Турция***Дилек ДУРСУН***Стамбульский университет Эсенюрт, Турция*

Целью данного исследования является определение влияния организационной приверженности и организационной справедливости на удовлетворенность работой. В исследовании использовалась родственная модель скрининга. Основное внимание исследования – примерно 17 000 бортпроводников, периодически меняющихся и работающих в аэропорту Стамбула, а также в компаниях гражданской авиации, учрежденных с января 2020 года. Выборочным методом выявлено 377 бортпроводников. Для сбора данных в исследовании использовались Мера Организационного Обязательства, Миннесотская Мера Рабочего Удовлетворения и Шкала организационной справедливости. Прогнозируемые изменения для анализа данных были выполнены с использованием многолинейного регрессионного анализа.

Исследование показало, что рассмотрение организационная приверженность бортпроводников в контексте поставленных параметров, эмоциональная, жизнестойкая и нормативная ответственность сотрудников влияют на удовлетворенность работой. Организационная справедливость бортпроводников также влияет на их удовлетворенность работой. Рассмотренное в рамках требований совместное восприятие взаимной, процессуальной и разделяемой справедливости не влияет на удовлетворенность работой.

Ключевые слова: Организационное обязательство, организационная справедливость, удовлетворенность работой, гражданская авиация, бортпроводник.

Коды ЖЕЛ: M1, M12, M54

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